

RETAIL DIGITAL PAYMENT SYSTEM IN INDIA: AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract

Electronic payment system has become very popular in India specially in last decade. Since demonetization in the year 2016 several methods of digital payments got their popularity and relevance. The penetration of internet facility, availability of smart phones at reasonable price to the major segment of the society, have been the causes for tremendous growth in the digital payment modes. The dimensions of banking have dramatically changed, the people are now more exposed and financially literate to adopt the modern methods of banking. Several steps such as Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojna, launch Rupay debit card and UPI have been the turning points in the financial inclusion. In precise the digital financial inclusion. As of February 2026, over 57 crore Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Accounts under (PMJDY) have been opened since inception in 2015, Approximately 40 crore Rupay debit cards have been issued to the beneficiaries. These accounts have around 2 lakh 94 thousands crore rupees as deposits as on February 2026.

Keywords: *Electronic Payment, UPI, PMJDY, RUPAY*

Introduction

Bank in an economy is like a heart which provides and circulates life blood i.e. finance. Banks are the centre around which all the economic activities revolve. Modern banks provide not just the facility of deposits and withdrawal but more than that. The products offered by a bank are getting more diverse as the diffusion of technology in banking sector increasing. In the past decade our banking sector has passed through many dramatic and revolutionary changes with respect to financial inclusion. More than 57 crore bank accounts have been opened under Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojna having more than 2 lakh 94 thousands crore rupees as deposits as on February 2026.

Not just the GDP and the income of the people have increased but the penetration of technology in the field of banking has increased too. Mobile and Internet revolution in the past decade has completely changed the dimensions of banking. The launch of retail payment system called UPI by the facilitator NPCI (National Payments Corporation of India) has completely changed all the equation in the banking. Since its inception in 2016, UPI has become the most favoured and convenient method of retail payments

in India. Starting from 21 banks offering UPI services in the year 2016 the number has reached 691 in the year 2026. The value of transaction which was around 1696 crore rupees in January 2017 has reached to rupees 28,33,481 crore in January 2026.

Post independence India got many private sectors bank but their financial health was not sound enough for the economic growth of the country. So, in 1955 State bank of India was established by nationalising Imperial Bank of India, in 1969, 14 banks and in the year 1980, 6 more banks were nationalised to provide safer, economical and accessible banking facilities to the citizen. Though in the year 1972, regional rural banks were established to cater the needs of the rural and economically backward population of the country. HSBC (Hongkong and Shanghai Banking Corporation) bank started first ATM facility in Mumbai in the year 1987. After liberalization of the economy post 1990 as more foreign banks got active and started offering personalised and digital banking services, it became necessary for the existing nationalised banks to offer digital banking facilities to be in the competition. Reserve Bank of India started electronic clearing services and MICR (magnetic ink character reader) facilities. In 1996, ICICI started offering online banking facilities to its

customers. Later HDFC, IndusInd and Citibank also started offering digital banking facilities. In the year 2004, RTGS (Real Time Gross Settlement) facility was introduced for the first time. The branches of the banks were brought under a single umbrella through CBS (Core Banking Solution). The introduction of NEFT and RTGS payment settlement system made fund transfer easier, convenient and economical as never before.

Review of related Literature

Many researches have been performed in the field of digital banking to enquire the adoption and diffusion of the service. Some of the selected research works are given below:

Garry Wei-Han Tan, Chee-Keong Chong, Keng-Boon Ooi and Alain Yee-Loong Chong

The study was done to find the responsible factors for the adoption of e-banking in Malaysia. The study was based on primary data collected from 231 students of a private university in Malaysia. Extended TAM (technology acceptance model) was used having variables such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, perceived financial cost, perceived security risk, social influence and intention to use.

Social influence, perceived usefulness, trust and perceived ease of use were found to affect the adoption of e-banking. However the study finds perceived financial cost and perceived security risk not having significant impact on e-banking adoption.

Nour-Mohammad Yaghoubi, Ebrahim Bahmani

This study was conducted to examine factors affecting adoption of e-banking in Isfahan province of Iran. They used an integrated model using TAM (technology acceptance model) and TPB (theory of planned behavior).

Perceived ease of use was found to be having a positive impact on attitudes towards the use of online banking and perceived usefulness. Perceived usefulness was found to have a positive impact on behavioral intention and attitude to use online banking.

Dr. Roshan Lal, Dr. Rajni Saluja

The study was conducted in Indian context to examine the growth of banks in adoption of technology. The study was secondary data based and used percentage, average etc. for analysis. They examine the computerization in public sector banks, the installation of ATMs, electronic payment system i.e. ECS, NEFT and electronic debit and credit cards payments.

Mohammad Shamsus Sadekin, Md. Abdul Hannan Shaikh

The study was conducted in Bangladesh to find the impact of e-banking specially the security factor in e-banking. They found electronic banking easier for customers to compare banks' services and products. Internet has emerged as a weapon for banks to satisfy their customers providing electronic banking, adequate legal

framework and security were found to be the essential factors for internet banking. They found several advantages of e-banking such as time saving, helpful in reducing unemployment, helpful in proper planning and monitoring of money.

Jaroslav Belas, Michal Koraus, Felix Kombo, Anton Koraus

The study was conducted in Slovakia to find the selected attributes of commercial banks security in relation to customer satisfaction. Security is a significant issue in commercial bank management and is connected to a large number of bank activities.

The researchers suggested the banks to provide a sound system for the safety of the customers account and showed a belief that biometric system will enhance the security of the customers account. They found customers also responsible for getting their account hacked and suggested to use strong measure such as antiviruses, antispam and antiphishing software.

F. Sameni Keivani, M. Jouzbarkand, M. Khodadadi, Z. Khalil Sourkouhi

In their study they found service quality of banks to be a major factor for retaining and surviving in the present age of competition. E-banking services are replacing traditional forms of banking services.

Tero Pikkarainen, Kari Pikkarainen, Heikki Karjaluoto, Seppo Pahlila

To find the factors influencing online banking acceptance the researchers used TAM with few additional factors namely perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived enjoyment, information on online banking, security and privacy and quality of internet connection.

Vidhya jolly

The study was conducted in Kochi, India to find out how much cost effective and popular is the online banking system.

Customers of lower age group were more often using e-banking than the customers of higher age group. Mode of banking and transaction cost were found to have a weak relationship. Most of the respondent found e-banking channel to be easy and convenient than traditional channels of banking.

Seif Obeid Al-Shabiel, Muhannad Akram Ahmad

The researchers integrated TAM and TPB model to provide a discussion on electronic banking in Jordan and identify the factors affecting acceptance of e-banking in Jordan. Integrating the TAM with TPB they have developed a model including enjoyment, self-efficacy, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived trust, subjective norm.

The proposed model finds that attitude towards use, subjective norms, perceived behavioural control and

perceived trust have a direct impact on the behavioural intention to accept the practice of e banking in Jordan.

Andre Redlinghuis, Chris Rensleigh

The paper was written to find the perception of consumers on information protection when using internet banking services and products. Internet banking provides benefits like convenience, efficiency and 24 hours availability etc. but the users sometimes face attacks via computer and internet viruses, phishing scams and internet hackers. The investment in adequate softwares and infrastructure is required for conducting secured transaction using electronic mode of banking.

Shilpan Vyas

The paper gives meaning, types, advantages and limitations of e-banking and also tries to show the impact of e-banking on traditional banking services. E-finance has become one of the most essential technological change in the financial industry. E-finance includes e-payment, e-trading and e-banking. E-banking transactions are much more cheaper than branch transactions. This could turn a large branch network into a comparative disadvantage, allowing e-banks to undercut "bricks and mortar banks".

Divya Singhal and V. Padhmanabham

This paper aims at identifying the important factors for internet banking based on respondents' perception on various internet applications. Private banks in India took internet application as a weapon of competitive advantage against the banking giants such as SBI and other public sector banks.

The researchers find the on bill payments and online ticketing are increasing. A majority of respondents find e-banking convenient and flexible. It provides speedy transaction facility at lower cost. The findings show that majority of the respondents are concerned with security of the transactions and agree that digital signature is the best way to have security of transaction.

Sonia Sharma

The paper makes a comparative study between traditional and electronic mode of banking. New innovations in the field of information technology have created new opportunities for financial sector but also generated some challenges as well.

The researcher concluded that e-banking has opened a new window of possibilities for the financial sector. Banks should provide customised services to their customers. The government of the country also has a vital role to perform by providing proper regulations regarding electronic transactions and also internet access among the countrymen.

Bahar Sanli, Elif Hobikoglu

They find electronic banking a tool for facing competition in terms of time, location and cost for banks in financial sector. The study is based on Turkish banking industry.

Their research shows that internet banking has gained great speed around the world in terms of adoption specially after the year 2000. They find security problem of technological system to be a big issue. Grievance redressal system should be quick enough to provide customer immediate solution of their problems specially when the customers find any sensitive movement in their account.

Sriram Devulapalli, Sai Karthik Oruganti

This study was conducted in Indian context and focuses on the impact of demonetisation on electronic banking usage. The paper describes the various advantages of e-banking such as convenience, flexibility, time saving and on the other hand several challenges i.e. low broadband internet penetration, banks reluctance to provide e-banking services, customers preference for traditional form of banking, security risk, impersonal form of banking, unawareness, regulations and legalities etc.

Payam Hanafizadeh, Mehdi Behboudi, Amir Abedini Koshksaray, Marziyeh Jalilvand, Shirkhani Tabar

This study provides insights into the factors affecting the adoption of mobile banking in Iran. They took a sample of 361 bank clients in Iran and latent variables of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, need for interaction, perceived risk, perceived cost, compatibility with life style, perceived credibility and trust were examined.

Trust was identified as the second most influential factor and the indicators of facilitating banking jobs was identified as more influential compared to usefulness and improving methods. Thus, facilitating banking jobs is more important in m-banking adoption. The perception of customer from security of transaction and sending and receiving information affects their use and reliance upon m-banking. It was recommended to design m-banking software in a way so that they can be learned easily and can be used by different groups of the society.

Ibrahi M. Al-Jabri, M. Sadiq Sohail

The research was conducted in Tuticorin district of Tamilnadu to find the awareness and satisfaction level towards e-banking. Transparency, accuracy, cost saving and speed are the factors for preferring e-banking services and social status, security, control over funds, time out feature and exchange of information are the motivating factors for the customers.

Hanudin Amin, Ricardo Baba, Mohd Zulkifli Muhammad

This study uses TAM (technology acceptance model) to investigate factors that determine an individual's intention to use mobile banking among customers in Labuan and Kota Kinabalu. In this study perceived credibility, perceived self-efficacy and normative pressure are added to enhance the understanding of customer acceptance of mobile banking beyond the general constructs used in TAM.

Akram Jalal, Jassim Marzooq, Hassan A. Nabi

The purpose of this research paper was to explore the impact of selected factors on the customers' intention to use internet banking in Bahrain. The technological and communication changes in present era has forced the banks to develop an technological channel to attract customers and improve their perception. The rapid technological diffusion makes the internet the best way to provide customers with banking services regardless of the limits of time and geography. Internet technology has changed the design and the way of delivering the financial services and as a result the banking industry has made continuous innovations especially in the field of communications and information technology that ultimately led to the emergence of the idea of what is known as the "online banking".

Samaneh Barati, Shahriar Mohammadi

In this paper the researchers have tried to find factors affecting acceptance of mobile banking and presented a new model. Citing various related works the researchers tries to find a new model. Technology acceptance model appeared to the most widely accepted among information systems researches. They find certain variables such as usage barrier, value barrier, risk barrier, tradition barrier and image barrier responsible for innovation resistance. Innovation resistance will have a negative effect on final acceptance of mobile banking. Facilitating conditions were found responsible for affecting perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness.

Saviour Lusaya, Brnwell Kalumba

This study investigated the challenges of adopting the use of e-banking by customers. Using a descriptive study, this study collected data from 50 respondents from the banking sector in Kasma.

They found that the availability of e-banking information affects e-banking usage, the education level of users also influences the e-banking usage. On the other hand they found that security was not significantly related with the use of e-banking. Hence the study finds information on e-banking to be the biggest challenge and security was not found as a challenge for e-banking adoption.

Nii Kwartei Perry-Quartey

This paper discusses e-banking various definitions, examples, advantages and limitations, electronic banking in Ghana and its impact on the profitability of banks in the Ghanaian banking industry. Researchers have recognized that it is possible for banks to improve their competitive stance and profitability by providing their clients with more electronic products and services.

Shumaila Yousafzai, John Pallister and Gordon Foxall

The present paper is concerned with finding the role of trust in internet banking adoption. Trust has been identified as the key to e-commerce because it is crucial wherever uncertainty and interdependence exist.

Customers' trust in internet banking transactions has some unique dimensions, that is, the impersonal nature of

the online environment, the extensive use of technology and the inherent uncertainty of using an open infrastructure. Trust in internet banking is a new and emerging area of interest in the field of marketing of financial services research.

Joyce Wangui Gikandi, Chris Bloor

The study was conducted in Kenya in the years 2005 and 2009. This was a comparative study to examine the change in factors influencing the adoption and effectiveness of e-banking in retail banking in Kenya.

From the study made cost reduction and enhanced ability to deal with customers were the main factors from e-banking usage. Along with this adoption of e-banking by other banks and demand of customers were also the key drivers for the adoption of e-banking by a majority of banks. Enhanced ability, competitive forces were also the key drivers between the duration of 2005 to 2009 in place of top level management initiative to adopt e-banking the role of IT department in adoption has risen this may be due to increased customer demand for such facilities.

Siriluck Rotchanakitumnual, Mark spece

Internet banking allows customers to have direct access to their financial information and to undertake financial transactions with no need to go to the bank. The paper is based on qualitative study to explore the perceptions of internet banking among corporate customers.

Objectives of the study

- 1) To examine the growth of digital payments systems in past few years.

Research Methodology

The study is based on the secondary data collected from NPCI website. The data for the past 3 years has been collected for UPI, IMPS and AEPS. A change in the value and volume of transactions is calculated with the help of MS-excel.

In the last few years retail digital payments have increased with a great pace. As shown in the table below in the year 2021-22 when there were only 71,769 million retail digital transactions having a value of 4,57,440 billion were performed. In the financial year 2024-25 the number of transactions were 2,21,679 against the value of 8,49,120 billion registering an incredible increase in retail payments in India.

Financial Year	Retail Digital Payments		Growth in Percentage	
	Volume (million)	Value (billion)	Volume	Value
F.Y.-2021-22	71,769	4,57,440	-	-
F.Y.-2022-23	1,13,695.60	5,87,390	58.42%	28.41%
F.Y.-2023-24	1,64,160.20	7,19,370	44.39%	22.47%
F.Y.-2024-25	2,21,679	8,49,120	35.04%	18.04%

Source: <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2240723®=3&lang=2>

Figure:1.1

In the above-mentioned data for retail digital payment system, UPI (unified payment interface) has emerged as the game changer registering more than 80% of the retail digital payments.

After comparing F.Y. 2021-22 with F.Y. 2024-25 it can be seen that the growth in value is of transaction is 85.62% and in the number of transactions is 208.88%. This fabulous rise in number of transactions shows how much retail payment system become popular amongst the users.

The growth of UPI (Unified Payment Interface)

Since its launch in the year 2016, UPI (Unified Payment Interface) has emerged as a game changer and completely revolutionized the retail payment system in India. Due to accuracy, speed and economy UPI has popularised dramatically in small value transactions.

The system was developed by NPCI (National Payment Corporation of India) which was adopted by the banks and later banks launched their specific banking applications based on UPI system making much more accessible and convenient for the users.

UPI (Unified Payment Interface)		
YEAR	Volume (in Mn)	Value (in Bn)
F.Y-2022-23	83751	139207
F.Y-2023-24	131165	199867
F.Y-2024-25	185866	260570

Figure:1.2

In the financial year 2024-25 UPI has recorded transactions of more than RS. 2,60,570 billion which shows a growth rate of 30.37% over the previous financial year (2023-24). In the same manner the number of transactions have increased 41.70% in comparison to the previous year (2023-24). At the end of financial year 2024-25 a total of 661 banks were providing the facility of UPI to their customers. The number of UPI service providing banks has risen by 15.56% in the financial year 2024-25.

The rate of growth 41.70% far more than the rate of growth in the value of transactions in financial year 2024-25 indicating, the number of transactions specially the small number of transactions have increased sharply.

AEPS (Adhar enabled payment system)

Though AEPS (Adhar enabled payment system) has not been dominating in terms of value but a very impactful system of retail digital payment system in India. Linking aadhar with payment system has been this system very attractive, transparent and secured. This system launched in the year 2011 by NPCI (National Payment Corporation of India). A vast number of Aadhar card holder in the country provided the base for this system to reach the underserved and every section of the society. The aim of financial inclusion can easily be achieved with the AEPS. The system provides withdrawal of money by using biometric authentication of the account holder at CSC (common service centre).

AEPS (Inter Bank) Txn over Micro ATM (e.g. Cash withdrawal/ Cash Deposit)		
YEAR	Volume (in Mn)	Value (in Bn)
F.Y-2022-23	1258	3418
F.Y-2023-24	1197	3210
F.Y-2024-25	1193	3061

Figure:1.3

In the financial year 2024-25 AEPS has recorded transactions of more than RS.3061 billion which shows a decrease of 4.65% over the previous financial year i.e. 2023-24. Though the rate of decline in value is less than the decline rate in F.Y. 2023-24 was 6.07% as compared to 2024-25 which. In the same manner the number of transactions have declined by a nominal rate of 0.31% in comparison to the previous year 2023-24 data.

The data shown above in the table is not very encouraging with respect to AEPS. The transaction value through AEPS is falling rapidly over the last few years. The penetration of information technology, increasing level of awareness among the users for UPI might be the cause for fall in the number and value of transactions through AEPS.

IMPS (Immediate Payment System)

IMPS (Immediate Payment System) was launched in 2010 provides instant money transfer facility 24*7. Funds can be transferred instantly from one bank to another without any hassle. Maximum of 5 Lakh rupee can be transferred per day though this limit varies from bank to bank. This system provides speedy, transparent and accurate 24*7 transfer of funds at very low cost. User require the transferee bank account number and IFSC or the MMID (Mobile Money Identifier) of transferee.

IMPS		
YEAR	Volume (in Mn)	Value (in Bn)
F.Y-2022-23	5654	55861
F.Y-2023-24	5992	64745
F.Y-2024-25	5625	71391

Figure:1.4

In the financial year 2024-25 the IMPS transaction has increased in value by a growth rate of 10.27% in comparison to previous year 2023-24. Though the number of transactions recorded in the same period shows a decline of 6.12 %. Which suggests that value per transaction has increased but the numbers of transactions are falling. In the F.Y. 2023-24 IMPS transaction in value registered a growth of 15.90% in comparison to previous year 2022-23 but the number of transactions rose with a comparatively low rate of 5.97%.

IMPS not being as popular as UPI in present scenario but it has its separate customer base due to an enhanced limit of 5 lakh rupees per day and being perceived much more secured and accurate.

Findings

- 1) UPI has shown drastic rise in its adoption by the users.
- 2) UPI covers more than 80% of the overall retail digital payments.
- 3) UPI specially after the launch of QR based payment system has gained more popularity.
- 4) Retail digital payments contributing in nation's economic growth by facilitating quick and accurate payments.
- 5) AEPS found to be losing its popularity as UPI coverage is increasing rapidly.
- 6) Concern for the safety and security of the digital payments is an important area for adoption of digital payment system.

Conclusions

As the data shows above, after telecommunication penetration and various efforts taken by the government, reserve bank of India and National Payment Corporation of India, incredible growth in the field of retail digital

payments is registered. We are getting closer and closer to the goal of financial inclusion. Financial services are now reaching even to the marginalized section of the society resulting in their economic assistance. The business base inside and even outside the country is increasing just because of various reforms in the financial sector.

But safety and security for the digital payment system is still a major concern for the users. Lack of awareness about the advantages of the digital system is also a matter of concern. Users are required to be educated more about the benefits that can be obtained by using digital payment system.

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